

A DIGITAL TOOLBOX FOR MUSICAL ANALYSIS OF COMPUTER MUSIC: EXPLORING MUSIC AND TECHNOLOGY THROUGH SONIC EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Following earlier research in which we used software to create interactive aural analyses of key works from the computer music repertoire, this paper introduces a new set of digital tools, TIAALS (Tools for Interactive Aural Analysis), designed to facilitate other musicologists, who may not themselves be programmers, in producing their own interactive aural analyses of computer music, or indeed music more generally.

The goal here is not to automate analysis but rather to provide tools that can enhance the conduct and presentation of music analysis using software to facilitate interactive and aural engagement with the music as sound. Using software in this way has significant advantages over purely written or paper-based analyses: it enables people to learn about both the music and the technology behind it through interactive sonic experience. The software tools can be used to present musical structures aurally using interactive charts, elements of which can be heard by clicking on them to play relevant audio segments. Charts can also be dynamic, changing to reflect the temporal progression of the work or controlled manually to highlight different features. Sonograms can also be “live” and interactive, allowing readers to manipulate the sound. The tools facilitate the incorporation of (annotated) videos, such as interviews/demonstrations by the composers and/or others involved in the musical or technical production of the work. Our previous analyses have also emulated the techniques composers used so “readers” can play with them, learning about the creative processes not just as abstract theory but through practical engagement with sound.

This paper introduces the main elements of TIAALS and shows how it can be used to incorporate many of the features described above into integrated analytical packages. We explain how the tools work and consider the potential,

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¹ The project website can be found at: <https://research.hud.ac.uk/institutes-centres/irimas/>. The full project team can be found listed there. The

as well as limitations, of the toolbox and the interactive aural approach.

1. BACKGROUND: FROM INTERACTIVE AURAL ANALYSIS TO IRIMAS

Digital technology offers significantly new possibilities for the way we engage with music, not only as listeners, composers, or performers, but also in analytical study. This is especially true for computer music where the sound world and the techniques employed may not be familiar to many readers and traditional notation and terminology may not be relevant [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. In response to this situation we developed an interactive aural approach to music analysis [6], an approach that uses software not primarily to automate analytical processes but rather to enhance human analytical engagement with the music as sound. In this way, for example, analytical charts can be in sound (charts in software with playback buttons embedded). The musical structure can not only be seen but heard. Likewise, the techniques used in a composition (be they musical or technical) are not just described verbally but presented in software emulations that can be manipulated by the reader. Again, the aural implications of what is discussed can immediately be experienced by readers as sound.

Since 2006 Interactive Aural Analysis (IAA) has been developed through a series of analyses [7, 8, 9, 10]. The most recent analyses appear in a book, *Inside Computer Music* [11], analysing nine key works from the computer music repertoire. The text is fully integrated with nine substantial software packages and 105 demonstration videos. The problem this paper discusses is how such an approach can be adopted by analysts and musicologists who are not expert programmers themselves, how might they analyse works in this way?

The IRiMaS project (2017-23, funded by an ERC Advanced Grant, grant agreement 741904)¹ set out to explore the potential of Interactive Aural Analysis for a much wider repertoire of music than just computer music (including aural/oral traditions from a variety of cultures, improvised music, and spectral music, as well the classical

authors of this paper were primarily responsible for the design and programming of TIAALS.

Western tradition). Its other main objective has been to develop as set of Tools for Interactive Aural Analysis (TIAALS)² to facilitate the production of analyses without the need for specialist programming skills. These tools have not been developed only for use with the repertoire of computer music but rather for the much broader range of styles and genres outlined above. In that context they have been thoroughly trialed and evaluated in consultation with a group of postgraduate and post-doctoral musicology researchers (non-programmers), the development taking place through iterative cycles of development and feedback. Musicological feedback has significantly influenced the design of the tools. Although developed for a very broad musical repertoire, we nonetheless believe these tools have significant potential for facilitating further interactive aural analyses of computer music and the remainder of this paper discusses how these tools might be used in the context of analysing works from that repertoire.

2. TIAALS

The TIAALS toolbox allows users to assemble a wide range of different interactive materials into a “project”. A project comprises one or more “pages”. Each page may contain a range of audio, video, text or graphic objects. A range of flexible navigation options can be introduced to move between pages in a non-linear manner. Objects can be tagged and filtered according to their tags. As previously stated, the principal intention with TIAALS is not to automate analysis but to enable analysts to engage with the analytical process in terms of their experience of the sound and to present their results accordingly. Some of the tools (e.g. the Interactive Aural Sonogram and the Descriptor Space) allow analysts and their readers to investigate the structure of the music using tools that process the sound. Others facilitate the production of analytical charts or maps that are aural and may be played interactively, placing listening at the centre of the analytical experience.

Other software packages for music analysis, such as Sonic Visualiser [14] or iAnalyse [15], provide important algorithms for analysing or annotating sound in specific ways. What is unique, we believe, about TIAALS is that it makes it possible for analysts to combine the results of different analytical approaches into a single digital document, producing an integrated analysis of the work.

We will begin by looking at some examples using different types of objects in TIAALS and then show how navigation options can be used. This paper is not intended as a thorough step-by-step manual to using TIAALS but as a brief discussion of the software’s potential and the implications of using this approach.

2.1 Creating Interactive Aural Charts

Interactive charts of various types are a key feature of IAA. They may be structural charts, taxonomies, genealogies, or

paradigmatic charts etc. TIAALS facilitates their development. The basic principle is that playback of sound segments can be triggered by clicking on audio buttons. These buttons (the sound objects themselves in fact) can be transparent or semi-transparent and placed over the appropriate part of a chart. The author links sound objects to a particular sound file and enters timings to select the specific sound segment to be played. The colour, size, labelling (if any), and transparency of the sound object can be adjusted. The chart itself can be made in TIAALS itself or imported as an image. So, for example, a chart made in Microsoft Word, or using the sophisticated graphics available in software such as Adobe Illustrator, can be imported as an image into TIAALS. Alternatively, if appropriate, an image from Finale or Sibelius using musical notation, or an existing image such as a geographical map might be imported. Figure 1 shows an interactive chart from our analysis of Natasha Barrett’s *The Lock* (in *Inside Computer Music*) originally hard-coded but which can now be recreated using TIAALS. It is a paradigmatic chart, with different types of sound shown as the paradigms on the horizontal axis and showing the distribution of these sounds through the work with time on the vertical axis. The sound objects (coloured rectangles) are placed over each element of the chart so that the relevant sounds can be played by clicking on them. In this way, a chart which might otherwise have seemed abstract presented only on the printed page, and difficult to relate to the music, is directly linked to aural experience.

Figure 1. An interactive aural paradigmatic chart from our analysis of Natasha Barrett’s *The Lock*

Charts can become overly complex containing an overload of information. Using TIAALS interactive charts can be filtered. If elements in a chart are created as separate objects, these objects can be tagged. Filtering can then be applied by selecting specific tags. Objects whose tags are not activated can either disappear altogether or remain greyed-

² We had previously sketched a small and limited prototype for TIAALS (in particular a prototype of the Interactive Sonogram) as part of our

earlier AHRC-funded TaCEM project (2012-2015) [12]. A first prototype of TIAALS as part of IRiMaS was presented in [13].

out in the background so the larger context can still be seen.

We used this approach in our analysis of Hildegard Westerkamp's *Beneath the Forest Floor* (in *Inside Computer Music*). Again, although this was originally hard-coded it can now be created using TIAALS). Our genealogy of the sounds in this work shows a complex web of source sounds and derivations, and connector lines show how these are related and variously combined to form the sections of the complete piece (at the top of the chart). The resulting dense chart can be filtered interactively to show only certain types of sound, or to just show sounds from the same genealogical branch. Figure 2 illustrates this with a screenshot. A video demonstration is also available.³

Figure 2. A dynamic chart from our analysis of Hildegard Westerkamp's *Beneath the Forest Floor*

Charts may also change dynamically to reflect the evolution of a musical structure over time. Musical structures are emergent, something not easy to represent on the printed page but possible to show in software.

2.2 Incorporating Annotated Video

In our analyses for *Inside Computer Music* videos played an important part. They included interviews with the composers and also sometimes with those who had helped with the production of the music, or developed the technology to enable the composition (e.g. Arshia Cont, Markus Noisternig, Gilbert Nouno, Miller Puckette, Olivier Warusfel). The composers talked about their aesthetic intentions (e.g. Francis Dhomont, Philippe Manoury, Hildegard Westerkamp) and the techniques they used (e.g. John Chowning, Trevor Wishart). Some demonstrated their use of the technology as they talked (Natasha Barrett, Cort Lippe, Barry Truax). Figure 3 shows a screenshot of Cort Lippe demonstrating his software at the computer. There is a significant benefit in hearing people speak as opposed

to simply reading a transcript, even more so if a live demonstration is included.

Using TIAALS, a video can be incorporated into a project simply by placing a video object on the page and selecting the file to be played. Clicking on the video object then plays the video in a separate pop-up window. Although we didn't do this in the earlier examples mentioned above, with TIAALS it is now possible to annotate the video, for example, adding written notes over the video (such as a translation of what is being said) or highlighting points of interest (e.g. circling a performer's gesture at a specific moment in time). Videos can also show the social context in which the music is performed where that forms an important part of the study.

Figure 3. Screenshot from video of Cort Lippe demonstrating his software for *Music for Tuba and Computer*

2.3 Interactive Aural Sonograms

Sonograms take data from an FFT of the sound and display this graphically on axes of time and frequency with colour or the grey scale indicating the amplitude at each moment in time for each frequency. Whilst in one sense showing everything there is to know about the sound, in practice in many situations the graphic representation does not clearly communicate much information to the reader when printed on the page. Our interactive sonogram is "live". Not only can it be played but the sound can be manipulated to explore the aural meaning of the sonogram representation. It is possible to "scrub" the sonogram, either with a full bandwidth cursor or one that is band-limited investigating the aural significance of features in the sonogram. Shapes can also be drawn on the sonogram, highlighting specific features. Filters can then be applied to these shapes during playback. As always, there is some distortion involved in the analysis/resynthesis process but nonetheless such investigation of the sonic world of the music can be revealing. In addition to such aural transformations the sonogram may also be annotated or segmented. The reader can interact with it and hear it in various ways. The sonogram object is in fact simply another way of viewing a sound object

³ A demonstration video of this chart being used interactively can be found at:

<https://huddersfield.box.com/s/nveujsw2i2rike2vq1dbhzaooti4pp3>.

The software itself, and many more demonstration videos can be found

via the Oxford University Press Companion Website accompanying the book *Inside Computer Music*.

and it is also possible to show a sonogram by changing the viewing mode of an existing sound object. A waveform view is also available. Figure 4 is a screenshot of a sonogram of part of Bernard Parmegiani’s *De Natura Sonorum*. It shows textual annotations, segmentation (identifying subsections of the work), and shapes drawn over the sonogram which can be used to filter specific sound features in the music.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the Interactive Aural Sonogram from our analysis (in progress) of Bernard Parmegiani’s *De Natura Sonorum*.

2.4 The Descriptor Space

The Descriptor Space object in TIAALS makes use of audio descriptors. The object is placed on the TIAALS page and a sound file selected. The audio is segmented and analysed using a range of audio descriptors and the user then has options of how to assign these parameters to x and y axes, size (segments are represented by circles) and colour. It is then possible to explore the distribution of these segments interactively, hearing how segments are related or distant in respect to the chosen descriptors. The path of the work’s temporal sequence through this map can also be traced. Figure 5 shows an example of a Descriptor Space. In this case the x-axis is assigned to time, the y-axis to centroid and size to magnitude.

Figure 5. Screenshot of a Descriptor Space from our analysis of Liza Lim’s *An Elemental Thing*.

2.5 Integrated Projects and Navigation

One of the key features of TIAALS is that it allows authors to combine many different tools and resources into a single integrated package or “project”. Furthermore, the tools are not just for use by the researcher – readers themselves are encouraged to interact with the materials as indicated above. In TIAALS a key idea is to place emphasis on analysis as open-ended and participatory.

Another aspect of this openness is the possibility of using TIAALS to create variable or non-linear paths through the materials. In creating any object the author has the option of adding a hyperlink or gate to that object so that clicking the object will navigate to another page. At its simplest this might mean creating an index page which leads to various other pages, but it also offers the possibility of creating alternative threads through the material.

3. LIMITATIONS

We hope to have demonstrated that in TIAALS we have created a significant and important resource for the development of musical analysis of computer music works as well as other repertoires. Inevitably, there are omissions and improvements that could be made. Whilst we have been fortunate to receive very generous funding to develop the IRiMaS project software development is a complex and time-consuming activity, and one that is never ending. We would hope that there will be opportunities for us, or others, to continue its development in the future.

There is one very specific omission from TIAALS that is inevitable. A significant feature of our earlier analyses was the emulation of the techniques used by composers to allow readers of our analyses to play with these techniques for themselves. The goal in making TIAALS was to create a way for musicologists to build their own analyses without the need for specialist technical knowledge or programming skills. The techniques used by a composer are very often specific to each composer, or even to an individual work. Emulating them, reverse-engineering the technology used by the composer as we did for *Inside Computer Music*, requires technical knowledge to understand the processes involved and skill to re-program them. It is also a very time-consuming exercise and sometimes dependent on the availability of information about obsolete systems. This therefore is something that could never be built into generic tools such as TIAALS, designed to be for widespread use. Nonetheless, for those with the necessary skills, we believe it is often an important way of gaining detailed knowledge about a work, and of

understanding more fully how technology and musical creativity inter-relate in a particular context.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Interactive aural analysis offers a distinctive new way to investigate computer music. It prioritises aural experience and interactive engagement with the music and its technology above abstract theoretical knowledge (though it is possible to combine both). TIAALS presents a means by which a wider range of people, including those with no technical and programming experience, can develop such analyses. It enables authors to combine sound, video, text and graphic objects with interactive sonograms and descriptor spaces to form integrated analytical documents in software. For readers it provides an open, interactive playground which places aural experience at the fore.

The knowledge gained through engaging with music using such an approach differs from more abstract analytical approaches. We would argue it is more wholistic, more experiential, perhaps reflecting anthropologist Tim Ingold's concern that "Knowing must be reconnected with being, epistemology with ontology, thought with life" [16]. In terms of music analysis, Kofi Agawu has written of the need "to restore to [analysis] a measure of improvisation, liberate it from the requirement of making propositional statements, and reconfigure its epistemological requirements to privilege play [...] encourag[ing] more thinking in music about music" [17]. We would hope that the use of TIAALS and the adoption of an interactive aural approach to analysis leads in this direction. It is an approach that has particular significance for computer music, where the sounds and techniques are often unfamiliar to readers and not suited to traditional analytical notation or terminology.

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